

CHORAK DOIRA TASHQARISIDA BIGARMONIK TENGLAMA UCHUN NOKORREKT QO‘YILGAN MASALA

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Annotatsiya. Outside of this quarter circle, the problem for the biharmonic equation incorrectly set is checked for conditional correctness and an approximate solution is constructed.

Key words: Laplace operator, incorrectness, uniqueness of solution, approximate solution.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu chorak doira tashqarisida bigarmonik tenglama uchun nokorrekt qo‘yilgan masala shartli korrektilikka tekshirilgan va taqribiy yechimi qurilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Laplas operatori, nokorrektlik, yechim yagonaligi, taqribiy yechim.

Ushbu maqolada chorak doira tashqarisida bigarmonik tenglama uchun nokorrekt qo‘yilgan masala shartli korrektilikka tekshirilgan va taqribiy yechimi qurilgan.

Masala. $D = \left\{ (\rho, \varphi) : a < \rho < +\infty, 0 < \varphi < \frac{\pi}{2} \right\}$ sohada quyidagi shartlarni

qanoatlantiruvchi $u(\rho, \varphi)$ funksiya topilsin:

$$\Delta^2 u(\rho, \varphi) = 0, \quad (\rho, \varphi) \in D, \quad (1)$$

$$u(\rho, 0) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} u(\rho, \frac{\pi}{2}) = 0, \quad a < \rho < +\infty, \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta u(\rho, 0) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi} \Delta u(\rho, \frac{\pi}{2}) = 0, \quad a < \rho < +\infty, \quad (3)$$

$$u(b, \varphi) = 0, \quad 0 \leq \varphi \leq \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial u(b, \varphi)}{\partial \rho} = f(\varphi), \quad 0 < \varphi < \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (5)$$

$$\lim_{\rho \rightarrow +\infty} u(\rho, \varphi) = \lim_{\rho \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} u(\rho, \varphi) = 0, \quad 0 < \varphi < \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (6)$$

bu yerda $a < b$, $f(\varphi)$ – berilgan funksiya, Δ – Laplas operatori.

Avval (1)-(6) masala nokorrekt qo‘yilganligini ko‘rsatamiz [1]. Haqiqatdan ham

$$f(\varphi) = \varepsilon \cdot \sin(2m + 1)\varphi$$

bo‘lganda

$$u_m(\rho, \varphi) = \varepsilon \frac{\rho^2 - b^2}{2b} \left(\frac{b}{\rho}\right)^{(2m+1)} \sin(2m+1)\varphi$$

funksiya (1)-(6) masalaning yagona yechimi bo'lishini bevosita tekshirib ko'rib ishonch hosil qilish mumkin.

Ixtiyoriy $\varepsilon > 0$ son uchun shunday $N > 0, C > 0$ sonlar topiladiki, $m > N$, $a < \rho < b$ bo'lganda

$$\left\| \frac{\partial u_m(b, \varphi)}{\partial \varphi} \right\|_{L_2(0, \frac{\pi}{2})} \leq \varepsilon \|u_m(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, \frac{\pi}{2})} > C > 0$$

bo'ladi. Bundan masalaning yechimi turg'un emasligi, ya'ni masala nokorrekt qo'yilganligi kelib chiqadi.

(1)-(6) masala yechimining turg'unligini xarakterlovchi quyidagi teorema o'rinli bo'ladi.

Teorema. Agar $u(\rho, \varphi)$ funksiya

$$\|u(a, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, \frac{\pi}{2})} \leq M, \quad (7)$$

$$\left\| \frac{\partial u(b, \varphi)}{\partial \rho} \right\|_{L_2(0, \frac{\pi}{2})} \leq \varepsilon,$$

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} f(\varphi) \sin \varphi d\varphi = 0$$

shartlarni bajarsa, u holda

$$\|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, \frac{\pi}{2})} \leq \frac{|\rho^2 - b^2|}{b^2 - a^2} M \left(\frac{a}{\rho}\right)^{2\lambda(\varepsilon)+1},$$

tengsizlik o'rinli bo'ladi. Bu yerda $\lambda(\varepsilon)$ son

$$\frac{b^2 - a^2}{2b} \left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^{2\lambda+1} = \frac{M}{\varepsilon},$$

tenglama ildizi.

Ushbu teoremadan (7) korrektilik to'plamida (1)-(6) masala yechimining yagonaligi kelib chiqadi.

Faraz qilaylik, $f(\varphi)$ funksiya δ aniqlikda berilgan bo'lsin, ya'ni bu funksiyaning o'rniga uning taqribiy qiymati $f_\delta(\varphi)$ funksiya berilgan bo'lib,

$$\|f(\varphi) - f_\delta(\varphi)\|_{L_2(0, \frac{\pi}{2})} \leq \delta$$

tengsizlik o'rinli bo'lsin.

(1)-(6) masalaning taqribiy yechimi sifatida quyidagi funksiyani olamiz [2]:

$$u_{n\delta}(\rho, \varphi) = \frac{\rho^2 - b^2}{2b} \sum_{m=1}^n \bar{a}_m \left(\frac{b}{\rho}\right)^{2m+1} \sin(2m+1)\varphi,$$

bu yerda $\bar{a}_m$ sonlar $f_\delta(\varphi)$ funksiyaning Fure koeffitsientlari.

(1)-(6) masalaning aniq va taqribiy yechimlari orasidagi farqni baholovchi quyidagi tengsizlikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\|u(\rho, \varphi) - u_{n\delta}(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, \frac{\pi}{2})} \leq |\rho^2 - b^2| \left[\left(\frac{b}{\rho}\right)^{2n+1} \frac{\delta}{2b} + \left(\frac{a}{\rho}\right)^{2n+3} \frac{2bM}{b^2 - a^2} \right].$$

Masalaning nokorrektligi.

Bevosita tekshirib ishonch hosil qilish mumkinki,

$$u_m(\rho, \varphi) = \varepsilon \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)}{2R_1} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^m \cos m\varphi \quad (m \geq 3), \quad (8)$$

funksiya (1) - (6) masalaning $f(\varphi) = \varepsilon \cos m\varphi$ bo‘lgandagi yechimi bo‘ladi. (8) formuladan ko‘rinadiki, ixtiyoriy o‘zgarmas $0 < \varepsilon < 1$, $c > 0$ sonlar uchun $\varphi \in (0, 2\pi)$, $\rho \in (R, R_1)$ shunday N topiladiki, $m > N$ bo‘lganda [3]

$$\left\| \frac{\partial u_m(R_1, \varphi)}{\partial \rho} \right\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} \leq \varepsilon; \quad \|u_m(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} > c > 0$$

tengsizliklar bajariladi:

Bundan ko‘rinadiki, masala yechimi turg‘un emas. Demak, qo‘yilgan masala nokorrekt masala.

Turg‘unlik bahosi.

Korrektlik to‘plami sifatida

$$\|u(R, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} \leq M,$$

tengsizlikni qanoatlantiruvchi funksiyalar to‘plamini olamiz.

Faraz qilaylik (1)-(6) masala yechimi mavjud va korrektlik to‘plamiga tegishli bo‘lsin

$u(\rho, \varphi)$ bigarmonik funksiyani ikkita $u_1(\rho, \varphi)$ va $u_2(\rho, \varphi)$ garmonik funksiyalar yig‘indisi

$$u(\rho, \varphi) = (\rho^2 - R_1^2)u_2(\rho, \varphi) + u_1(\rho, \varphi) \quad (9)$$

ko‘rinishda yozish mumkinligidan foydalanib, (1) - (6) masalani quyidagi ikkita masalaga keltiramiz:

1) $D = \{ (\rho, \varphi) : R < \rho < +\infty, 0 \leq \varphi \leq 2\pi \}$ sohada

$$\Delta u_1(\rho, \varphi) = 0, \quad (\rho, \varphi) \in D, \quad (10)$$

$$u_1(R_1, \varphi) = 0, \quad 0 \leq \varphi \leq 2\pi, \quad (11)$$

$$u_1(\rho, \varphi + 2\pi) = u_1(\rho, \varphi), \quad \lim_{\rho \rightarrow \infty} u_1(\rho, \varphi) = 0(1), \quad R < \rho < +\infty, \quad (12)$$

shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u_1(\rho, \varphi)$ funksiya topilsin.

2) $D = \{ (\rho, \varphi) : R < \rho < +\infty, 0 \leq \varphi \leq 2\pi \}$ sohada

$$\Delta u_2(\rho, \varphi) = 0, \quad (\rho, \varphi) \in D, \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_2(R_1, \varphi)}{\partial \rho} = \frac{1}{2R_1} f(\varphi), \quad 0 < \varphi < 2\pi \quad (14)$$

$$u_2(\rho, \varphi + 2\pi) = u_2(\rho, \varphi), \quad \lim_{\rho \rightarrow \infty} u_2(\rho, \varphi) = 0(1), \quad R < \rho < +\infty \quad (15)$$

shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u_2(\rho, \varphi)$ funksiya topilsin.

Birinchi masala garmonik davom ettirish masalasi bo'lib [1], ushbu masala echimining yagonaligidan $u_1(\rho, \varphi) = 0$ yechimga ega bo'ladi. Ikkinchi masalani hal etishda o'zgaruvchilarni ajratish usulidan foydalanamiz.

(13) - (15) masala yechimini

$$u_2(\rho, \varphi) = F(\rho)\Phi(\varphi) \quad (16)$$

ko'rinishda qidiramiz. (16) dan ikkinchi tartibli hosilalar olib, (13) ga qo'yamiz.

Natijada

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial F(\rho)}{\partial \rho} \right) \Phi(\varphi) + \frac{1}{\rho^2} F(\rho) \Phi''(\varphi) = 0,$$

$$-\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial F(\rho)}{\partial \rho} \right) \Phi(\varphi) = \frac{1}{\rho^2} F(\rho) \Phi''(\varphi).$$

Oxirgi ifodani $\frac{1}{\frac{1}{\rho^2} F(\rho) \hat{O}(\varphi)}$ ga ko'paytirib, λ ga tenglab,

$$\frac{\frac{d}{d\rho} \left(\rho \frac{dF(\rho)}{d\rho} \right)}{\frac{1}{\rho} F(\rho)} = -\frac{\Phi''(\varphi)}{\Phi(\varphi)} = \lambda$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Bundan esa quyidagi

$$\Phi''(\varphi) + \lambda \Phi(\varphi) = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\rho \frac{d}{d\rho} \left(\rho \frac{dF(\rho)}{d\rho} \right) - \lambda F(\rho) = 0 \quad (18)$$

oddiy differensial tenglamalarga ega bo'lamiz. Bunda

$$u_2(\rho, \varphi + 2\pi) = u_2(\rho, \varphi), \quad R < \rho < +\infty$$

shartlarga ko'ra

$$\Phi(\varphi + 2\pi) = \Phi(\varphi)$$

bo'lgani uchun $\sqrt{\lambda_n} = m$, m – butun son ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

U holda (17) tenglamaning umumiy yechimi

$$\hat{O}_n(\varphi) = \alpha_m \cos m\varphi + \beta_m \sin m\varphi, \quad (m = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots) \quad (19)$$

ko'rinishda ekanligini topamiz.

($m = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$) bo'lganda (18) tenglamaning umumiy yechimi ushbu

$$F_0 = A_0 + B_0 \ln \rho, \quad F_m(\rho) = A_m \rho^m + B_m \rho^{-m} \quad (m = 1, 2, 3, \dots) \quad (20)$$

ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi.

Bu qo'yilgan masala yechimi uchun $F(+\infty)$ chegaralangan bo'lishi kerak.

Shuning uchun (1,19) dan

$$F_0(\rho) = A_0, \quad F_m(\rho) = B_m \rho^{-m}, \quad (m = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

bo'ladi.

Shunday qilib, qaralayotgan tenglama yechimi

$$u_2(\rho, \varphi) = A_0 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \rho^{-m} [A_m \cos m\varphi + B_m \sin m\varphi] \quad (21)$$

ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi. Bu erda A_m, B_m ixtiyoriy o'zgarmas sonlar.

Endi chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantirishini tekshiramiz.

$$u_2(R_1, \varphi) = \frac{1}{2R_1} f(\varphi), \quad (22)$$

$$f(\varphi) = \frac{1}{2} a_0 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (a_m \cos m\varphi + b_m \sin m\varphi). \quad (23)$$

bu yerda,

$$a_m = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(\varphi) \cos m\varphi d\varphi, \quad b_m = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(\varphi) \sin m\varphi d\varphi$$

a_m, b_m - $f(\varphi)$ funksiyaning Fur'e koeffitsientlari.

(22) ning o'ng tomonidagi $f(\varphi)$ o'rniga (23) ni qo'yib, mos koeffitsientlarini

tenglaymiz va $A_0 = \frac{1}{4R_1} a_0, A_m = \frac{a_m R^{m-1}}{2}, B_m = \frac{b_m}{2} R_1^{m-1}$ ni topamiz.

Topilganlarni o'rniga qo'ysak, chegaraviy shartni qanoatlantiruvchi yechim

$$u_2(\rho, \varphi) = \frac{1}{2R_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} a_0 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho} \right)^m (a_m \cos m\varphi + b_m \sin m\varphi) \right) \quad (24) \text{ ko'rinishga ega}$$

bo'ladi. Bu erda a_m, b_m - $f(\varphi)$ funksiyaning Fur'e koeffitsienti.

Shunday qilib, (1) – (6) masalaning yechimi (9) formulaga ko'ra

$$u(\rho, \varphi) = \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)}{2R_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} a_0 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho} \right)^m (a_m \cos m\varphi + b_m \sin m\varphi) \right) \quad (25)$$

ko‘rinishda yoziladi. Bu yerda

$$a_m = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(\varphi) \cos m\varphi d\varphi, \quad b_m = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(\varphi) \sin m\varphi d\varphi,$$

a_m, b_m - $f(\varphi)$ funksiyaning Fur'e koeffitsientlari.

(25) yechim (6) shartni bajarishi uchun

$$a_m = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(\varphi) \cos d\varphi = 0, \quad (m = 0, 1, 2, \dots), \quad b_m = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(\varphi) \sin d\varphi = 0, \quad (m = 1, 2, \dots)$$

shartlar bajarilishi kerak. Shuning uchun (1)- (6) masala yechimi

$$u(\rho, \varphi) = \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)}{2R_1} \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^m (a_m \cos m\varphi + b_m \sin m\varphi) \quad (26)$$

ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi.

(1)- (6) masala yechimining turg‘unligini xarakterlovchi quyidagi teorema o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

Teorema. Agar $u(\rho, \varphi)$ funksiya

$$\|u(R, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} \leq M, \quad (27)$$

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\partial u(R_1, \varphi)}{\partial \rho} \cos m\varphi d\varphi = 0, \quad m = 0, 1, 2,$$

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\partial u(R_1, \varphi)}{\partial \rho} \sin m\varphi d\varphi = 0, \quad m = 1, 2,$$

$$\left\| \frac{\partial u(R_1, \varphi)}{\partial \rho} \right\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} \leq \varepsilon \quad (28)$$

munosabatlarni qanoatlantirsa, u holda

$$\|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} \leq \frac{|\rho^2 - R_1^2| \cdot M}{R_1^2 - R^2} \left(\frac{R}{\rho}\right)^{\lambda(\varepsilon)} \quad (29)$$

tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

Bu yerda $\lambda(\varepsilon)$ son

$$\frac{R_1^2 - R^2}{2R_1} \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{\lambda} = \frac{M}{\varepsilon} \quad (30)$$

trantsendent tenglama ildizi.

Isbot. (1) - (6) masalaning yechimini (27) korrektilik to‘plamida

$$u(\rho, \varphi) = \frac{\rho^2 - R_1^2}{2R_1} \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^m (a_m \cos m\varphi + b_m \sin m\varphi), \quad (26)$$

ko‘rinishda yozish mumkin.

(26) tenglikdan normaning ta‘rifiga ko‘ra

$$\|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0,2\pi)}^2 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} u^2(\rho, \varphi) d\varphi = \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} c_m^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^{2m} \quad (31)$$

tenglik kelib chiqadi. Bu yerda $c_m^2 = a_m^2 + b_m^2$.

(27) va (28) shartlardan esa

$$\|u(R, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0,2\pi)}^2 = \frac{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2m} c_m^2 \leq M^2 \quad (32)$$

$$\left\| \frac{\partial u(R, \varphi)}{\partial \rho} \right\|_{L_2(0,2\pi)}^2 = \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} c_m^2 \leq \varepsilon^2 \quad (33)$$

tengsizliklarga ega bo‘lamiz.

(31) funksionalni (32) va (33) shartlar ostida shartli maksimumga tekshiramiz.

Buning uchun Lagranj funksiyasini tuzamiz:

$$L(c_m, \lambda, \mu) = \frac{(\rho^2 - R^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} c_m^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^{2m} + \\ + \lambda \left[\frac{(R^2 - R_1^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2m} c_m^2 - M^2 \right] + \mu \left[\sum_{m=3}^{\infty} c_m^2 - \varepsilon^2 \right]$$

Bu funksiyaning c_m , λ , μ argumentlar bo‘yicha olingan xususiy hosilalarni nolga tenglaymiz.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial c_m} = 2c_m \left[\frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^{2m} + \lambda \frac{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2m} + \mu \right] = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2m} c_m^2 - M^2 = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \mu} = \sum_{m=3}^{\infty} c_m^2 - \varepsilon^2 = 0.$$

Oxirgi uchta munosabatdan (31) ning o‘ng tomonidagi yig‘indi maksimumga erishishi uchun c_m koeffitsientlar quyidagi 3 ta shartdan birini qanoatlantirishi kelib chiqadi:

1. $c_m^2 = 0$, $m \neq p, q$, $p < q$,

2. $c_p^2 \neq 0, c_q^2 = 0,$
3. $c_p^2 = 0, c_q^2 \neq 0.$

Aytaylik, birinchi shart bajarilsin. U holda

$$\begin{cases} c_p^2 + c_q^2 = \varepsilon^2 \\ \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2p} c_p^2 + \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} c_q^2 = \frac{4R_1^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} M^2 \end{cases}$$

sistemaga ega bo‘lamiz. Bu sistemani yechib, c_p^2 va c_q^2 noma'lum koeffitsientlarni topamiz:

$$c_p^2 = \frac{\varepsilon^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} - \frac{4R_1^2 M^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2}}{\left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} - \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2p}} \geq 0$$

$$c_q^2 = \frac{\frac{4R_1^2 M^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} - \varepsilon^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2p}}{\left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} - \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2p}} \geq 0$$

$p < q$ bo‘lgani uchun har doim yuqoridagi tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

$c_p^2 \geq 0$ va $c_q^2 \geq 0$ ekanligidan

$$\varepsilon^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} - \frac{4R_1^2 M^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} \geq 0,$$

$$\frac{4R_1^2 M^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} - \varepsilon^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2p} \geq 0$$

tengsizliklar kelib chiqadi.

Natijada quyidagi tengsizlikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2\rho} \leq \frac{4R_1^2 M^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} \\ \varepsilon^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} \geq \frac{4R_1^2 M^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} \end{cases}$$

$$\frac{R_1^2 - R^2}{2R_1} \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^\rho \leq \frac{M}{\varepsilon} \leq \frac{R_1^2 - R^2}{2R_1} \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^q$$

Topilgan c_p^2 va c_q^2 larning ifodalarini (26) ga qo'yib, $p, q \rightarrow \lambda(\varepsilon)$ da limitga o'tamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)}^2 &= \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^{2\rho} c_p^2 + \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^{2q} c_q^2 \leq \\ &\leq \lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow \lambda(\varepsilon) \\ q \rightarrow \lambda(\varepsilon)}} \left\{ \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^p \frac{\varepsilon^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2\rho} - \frac{4R_1^2 M^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2}}{\left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} - \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2\rho}} + \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{4R_1^2} \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho}\right)^{2q} \frac{\frac{4R_1^2 M^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} - \varepsilon^2 \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2\rho}}{\left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} - \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2\rho}} \right\} = \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} M^2 \left(\frac{R}{\rho}\right)^{2\lambda(\varepsilon)} \\ \|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} &\leq \frac{|\rho^2 - R_1^2|}{R_1^2 - R^2} M \left(\frac{R}{\rho}\right)^{\lambda(\varepsilon)} \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerda $\lambda(\varepsilon)$ - (30) trantsendent tenglamaning ildizi.

Aytaylik, ikkinchi shart bajarilsin:

$c_q^2 = 0$, $c_p^2 \neq 0$ bo'lsin. U holda

$$\begin{cases} c_p^2 = \varepsilon^2 \\ \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2\rho} c_p^2 = M^2 \cdot \frac{4R_1^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} \end{cases}$$

bo'ladi.

(31) tenglikka ko'ra

$$\|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)}^2 \leq \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} M^2 \left(\frac{R}{\rho}\right)^{2\lambda(\varepsilon)}$$

hosil bo'ladi. Bundan esa

$$\|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} \leq \frac{|\rho^2 - R_1^2|}{R_1^2 - R^2} M \left(\frac{R}{\rho}\right)^{\lambda(\varepsilon)}$$

kelib chiqadi. Bu yerda $\lambda(\varepsilon)$ - (30) trantsendent tenglamaning ildizi.

Aytaylik, uchinchi shart bajarilsin:

$c_q^2 \neq 0$, $c_p^2 = 0$ bo'lsin. U holda

$$\begin{cases} c_q^2 = \varepsilon^2 \\ \left(\frac{R_1}{R}\right)^{2q} c_q^2 = M^2 \cdot \frac{4R_1^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} \end{cases}$$

bo'ladi. (31) ga ko'ra

$$\|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)}^2 \leq \frac{(\rho^2 - R_1^2)^2}{(R_1^2 - R^2)^2} M^2 \left(\frac{R}{\rho}\right)^{2\lambda(\varepsilon)}$$

bo'ladi. Bundan esa

$$\|u(\rho, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0, 2\pi)} \leq \frac{|\rho^2 - R_1^2|}{R_1^2 - R^2} M \left(\frac{R}{\rho}\right)^{\lambda(\varepsilon)}$$

kelib chiqadi. Bu yerda $\lambda(\varepsilon)$ - (30) trantsendent tenglamaning ildizi. Shu bilan teorema isbot bo'ldi.

Ushbu teoremadan korrektilik to'plamida qo'yilgan masala yechimining yagonaligi kelib chiqadi.

Taqribiy yechimni qurish.

Matematik fizikaning qandaydir masalasini Tixonov ma'nosida korrektiligi ko'rsatilgandan keyin bu masalaning taqribiy yechimini qurish muammosi vujudga keladi.

Nokorrekt qo'yilgan masalalarning taqribiy yechimlarini qurish usullari ishlab chiqilganiga ancha bo'ldi. Tixonov 1963 yili nokorrekt qo'yilgan masalalarni taqribiy yechishga yangicha yondashishni ishlab chiqdi. Bu usulning nazariyasi regulyarlashtiruvchi oilalar tushunchasi bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Aytaylik klassik ma'noda nokorrekt qo'yilgan matematik fizika masalasi berilgan bo'lsin.

α parametrga bog'liq bo'lgan masalalar oilasi qaralayotgan nokorrekt masalaga nisbatan regulyarlashtiruvchi oila deyiladi, agar quyidagi ikkita shart bajarilsa:

1) $\forall \alpha > 0$ son uchun masalalar oilasiga qarashli bo'lgan masala klassik korrekt qo'yilgan.

2) agar berilgan funksiyalar shunday bo'lsaki, bunda qaralayotgan nokorrekt masala yechimi mavjud bo'lsa, u holda $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ da masalalar oilasidagi xuddi shunday berilgan funksiyalarga bog'liq masala yechimlari ketma - ketligi nokorrekt masala yechimiga intiladi.

α ni regulyarlashtirish parametri deyiladi. Ba'zida n butun sonli parametrda bog'liq regulyarlashtiruvchi oilalar qaraladi va bunda ikkinchi shartda oilaga qarashli bo'lgan masala yechimini $n \rightarrow \infty$ da qaralayotgan nokorrekt masala yechimiga intilishi talab etiladi.

α yoki n parametrda bog'liq operatorlar oilasi berilgan nokorrekt masalaga nisbatan regulyarlashtiruvchi operatorlar oilasi deyiladi, agar quyidagi ikki shart bajarilsa:

- 1) $\forall \alpha > 0$ ($n > 0$) uchun oiladagi har bir operatorlar uzluksiz bo'lsa;
- 2) $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ ($n \rightarrow \infty$) bo'lgan holda $B_\alpha f_\delta \rightarrow Bf$ bo'lsa, bu yerda $B_\alpha f_\delta$ - taqribiy yechim, Bf – aniq yechim.

n butun sonli parametrda bog'liq holda quyidagicha aniqlangan B_n chiziqli operatorlar oilasini qaraymiz:

$$B_n f(\phi) = \frac{\rho^2 - R_1^2}{2R_1} \sum_{m=3}^n \left(\frac{R_1}{\rho} \right)^m (a_m \cos m\phi + b_m \sin m\phi)$$

bu yerda, $a_m = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(\phi) \cos m\phi d\phi$, $b_m = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(\phi) \sin m\phi d\phi$, $f(\phi)$ funksiya-ning Fur'e koeffitsienti.

Agar $f(\phi)$ va $u(\rho, \phi)$ yechim $L_2(0, 2\pi)$ Gilgbert fazosining elementlari deb qaralsa, u holda B_n operatorlar oilasi regulyarlashtiruvchi bo'ladi [3].

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